

P: ISSN No. 2394-0344
E: ISSN No. 2455-0817

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/67980

VOL.- X , ISSUE- III June - 2025
Remarking An Analisation

Effect of Kapalbhathi on Body Mass Index among Collegians

Paper Id : 20334 Submission Date : 2025-05-04 Acceptance Date : 2025-05-22 Publication Date : 2025-05-25
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16407190

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Abstract

The present study investigates the effect of Kapalbhathi, a yogic kriya, on Body Mass Index (BMI) among young college students. With increasing cases of obesity and lifestyle-related disorders in youth, yoga offers a non-pharmacological, cost-effective, and accessible approach to health management. A sample of 40 college students (aged 17–25 years) were selected and divided equally into experimental and control groups. The experimental group practiced Kapalbhathi for 40 minutes on 03 alternate days a week, for a total of 12 weeks. Pre-test and post-test measurement of BMI was recorded. The findings indicated a statistically significant reduction and reduction in BMI among the experimental group, suggesting the efficaciousness of Kapalbhathi as a beneficial practice in managing body weight.

Keywords Kapalbhathi, Yoga, BMI, Obesity, Weight Management.

Introduction

The modern age is the age of machines. In the present times, it has become difficult to live without it. At present, the dependence of people on machines has increased, as a result of which their physical ability and activity has decreased. People now want to reduce physical exertion and find solutions to all problems at the brain level. Due to lack of labor, wrong eating habits and bad lifestyle, today's youth is also moving towards obesity. Body mass index is a widely accepted indicator of body fat and health risk. Shatkarma has been described in Gheranda Samhita and Hatha Yoga Pradipika. Shatkarma is the science of establishing harmony between the life flows of the two rivers Ida and Pingala, which helps in achieving physical and mental purity and balance. Dhauti, Basti, Nauli, Neti, Tratak and Kapalbhathi are the six actions of Shatkarma. Kapalbhathi is an important action of yoga. Kapal means brain and Bhati means light or cleanliness, hence Kapalbhathi means the process of enlightening and purifying the brain. Just as it is necessary to purify the Nadis, similarly the mental alertness should also be freed from the bonds that bind it to the physical world. Kapalbhathi is used for this. The purpose of Kapalbhathi action is to raise the life force from the Mooladhara and focus it on the Aagya Chakra. Kapalabhati is practiced to balance the three doshas viz. vata, pitta and kapha, to awaken and balance the Anamaya, Prana maya and Mano maya koshas, to purify the entire body and to increase the concentration of oxygen in the body. Yoga, especially shatkriyas like Kapalabhati, have an important role in improving metabolic function and weight management. Kapalabhati involves rapid forceful exhalation and passive inhalation. It stimulates the abdominal organs, improves digestion, strengthens the lungs and also reduces obesity by increasing energy expenditure.

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Remarking An Analisation

- Objective of study**
1. To examine the effect of kapalbhathi on Body Mass Index in young girls' college students.
 2. To examine the effect of kapalbhathi on Body Mass Index in Young boys' college students

Review of Literature

Rahul et al. (2010) found that practice of kapalbhathi pranayama had significant effect on lean body mass.

Gopal et al. (2011) reported yogic beathing exercises improve metabolic rate and reduce body fat.

Sahay (2012) found that yogic practices significantly influence Body Mass Index, especially in adolescent and young.

Sharma et al. (2014) reported that a significant decrease in Body Mass Index and waist circumferences among adults after 12 weeks of pranayama practices.

Sinha and Jain (2019) found that yoga-based interventions improved physical and mental health parameters including body Mass index.

Kushwaha et al. (2024) found that Pranayama and Meditation practices significantly reducing BMI among university students.

Methodology**Participants:**

Collegians include young college students. Young college girls and young college boys have been included in this study. 40 students Digvijai Nath P. G. College students (20 males, 20 females) aged between 17 to 25 years were randomly selected.

Design:

Experimental study with pre-test and post -test control group design.

Groups:

Experimental Group -I (Boys) (n=10): Practiced kapalbhathi alternate days per week.

Experimental Group-II (Girls) (n=10): Practiced Kapalbhathi alternate days per week.

Control group-I (Boys) (n=10): No yogic practice.

Control group-II (Girls) (n=10): No yogic practice.

Intervention procedure:

Duration: 12 weeks.

Frequency: 3 alternate days per week. (Tuesday, Thursday and Saturday)

Session Length: 40 minute per day

Experimental Treatment:

Total time duration: 40 min

Starting the class with 'AUM' chanting and prayer: 02 min

S.R. No. & Variable	Group	Mean	SD	SEM	N
1 BMI	Pre-test	22.190	3.975	1.257	10
2 BMI	Post-test	22.140	3.969	1.255	10

P valve equals 0.2443

t = 1.2457 df = 9

Standard error of differences = 0.040

The control group showed this difference is considered to be not statistically significant.

Table 3. Experimental Group-II (Boys)

S.R. No. & Variable	Group	Mean	SD	SEM	N
1 BMI	Pre-test	20.490	3.319	1.050	10
2 BMI	Post-test	20.250	3.187	1.008	10

P value equals 0.0051

t =3.6742 df = 9

Standard error of difference = 0.065

This experimental group showed a statistically significant reduction in BMI after 12 weeks of kapalbhati training.

Table 4. Control Group-II (Boys)

S.R. No. & Variable	Group	Mean	SD	SEM	N
1 BMI	Pre-test	20.500	3.753	1.187	10
2 BMI	Post-test	21.470	3.427	1.084	10

P value equals 0.3593

t =0.9660 df = 9

Standard error of difference = 1.004

The control group showed this difference is considered to be not statistically significant

The present study was conducted to examine the effect of Kapalbhathi Pranayama on Body Mass Index (BMI) among young college students, with a specific comparison between male and female participants. The findings revealed that Kapalbhathi had a statistically significant effect on reducing BMI in young college boys, whereas in young college girls, BMI showed a reduction but was not statistically significant. These results suggest that gender may play a role in the responsiveness to yogic practices like Kapalbhathi, possibly due to differences in metabolic rate, fat distribution, hormonal profile, and physical activity levels between males and females. Previous research supports the effectiveness of Kapalbhathi in reducing abdominal fat and improving metabolism, which may be more immediately evident in males due to higher visceral fat and more responsive fat mobilization. On the other hand, females typically have higher subcutaneous fat, which might require longer duration or more intense intervention to observe significant changes in BMI. Another possible reason for the lesser impact in females could be variations in adherence, hormonal cycles, or dietary patterns which were not controlled in this study.

Conclusion

Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that:

1. Kapalbhathi Pranayama is effective in significantly reducing BMI in young college boys.
2. Although there was a reduction in BMI among young college girls, the change was not statistically significant.

These findings indicate that gender differences may influence the effectiveness of Kapalbhathi in managing body composition. While boys may experience more rapid changes in BMI with Kapalbhathi, girls may require a longer duration, additional dietary modifications, or combined interventions for significant results. Therefore, Kapalbhathi can be recommended as a safe and effective yogic practice for weight management, especially in male youth, while further studies are suggested to evaluate long-term effects in females.

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